

Study of cumulative properties of supramolecular complex of ivermectin

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Received by the editorial board: 28.05.2019; accepted for publication: 14.10.2019

Annotation

Research objective: to study the cumulative properties of the supramolecular complex of ivermectin.

Materials and Methods. The studies were carried out in the vivarium of the K. I. Skryabin All-Russian Scientific Research Institute of Infectious Diseases. For the experiment 20 mongrel white rats weighing 180 g were selected and divided into experimental and control groups of 10 animals each. To determine the coefficient of cumulation we used a method based on animal death at repeated administration of the drug - subchronic toxicity test in accordance with the "Guidelines for experimental (preclinical) study of new pharmacological substances". Rats of the experimental group were administered the drug orally during the first four days at a dose of 35.5 mg/kg, equal to 1/10 of the previously established single LD50 (298.0 mg/kg). Then every next four days the dose was increased 1.5 times. The control group of rats was injected with 2 ml of water each. The experiment was carried out for 28 days. During the whole experiment the animals were monitored, taking into account their condition and degree of activity.

Results and discussion. According to the accepted classification, the supramolecular complex of ivermectin belongs to the group of substances with weak cumulative properties, as the cumulation coefficient is 6.05 (toxicity group IV).

Keywords: supramolecular complex, ivermectin, arabinogalactan, polyvinylpyrrolidone, cumulation, white rats.

For citation: Zashchepkina V. V. V. Study of cumulative properties of supramolecular complex of ivermectin // *Russian Journal of Parasitology*. 2019. T. 13. № 4. C. 72-76. <https://doi.org/10.31016/1998-8435-2019-13-4-72-76>

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The Study of the Cumulative Properties of the Supramolecular Complex of Ivermectin

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Received on: 28.05.2019; accepted for printing on: 14.10.2019

Abstract

The purpose of the research is to study the cumulative properties of the supramolecular complex of ivermectin.

Materials and methods. Studies were conducted in the vivarium of the VNIIGIS named after K. I. I. Skrzabin. For the purpose of the experiment, 20 outbred white rats weighing 180 g were selected, which were divided into experimental and control groups of 10 animals each. To determine the cumulation coefficient, we used a method taking into account the death of animals upon repeated administration of the drug - a test of subchronic toxicity in accordance with the "Guidelines for the experimental (preclinical) study of new pharmacological substances". For the rats in the experimental group the drug was administered orally during the first four days at a dose of 35.5 mg/kg equal to 1/10 of the previously established single LD₅₀ (298.0 mg/kg). Then, the dose was increased by 1.5 times every next four days. The rats in the control group were injected with 2 ml of water. The experiment was carried out for 28 days. Throughout the experiment, animals were monitored, considering their condition and degree of activity.

Results and discussion. According to the accepted classification, the supramolecular complex of ivermectin belongs to the group of substances with weakly expressed cumulative properties, since the cumulation coefficient is 6.05 (IV toxicity group).

Keywords: supramolecular complex, ivermectin, arabinogalactan, polyvinylpyrrolidone, cumulation, white rats.

For citation: Zashchepkina V. V. V. Study of the cumulative properties of the supramolecular complex of ivermectin. *Rossiyskiy parazitologicheskiy zhurnal = Russian Journal of Parasitology*. 2019; 13 (4): 72-76.

<https://doi.org/10.31016/1998-8435-2019-13-4-72-76>

Introduction

In connection with the use of chemotherapeutic antiparasitic agents there is a problem of their evaluation from the point of view of safety of their use in practice in order to exclude possible remote effects on animals and humans. This problem can be solved by toxicological evaluation taking into account the cumulative activity of new pharmacological agents and especially long-acting preparations. With repeated daily use of the drug may accumulate in the body (cumulation of the substance).

Cumulative properties - accumulation of effect at repeated administration of toxic substances; determined on the basis of a quantitative indicator - cumulation coefficient.

Before conducting chronic toxicological experiments, it is necessary to determine the cumulation index of a pharmacological substance - the ratio of LD₅₀ for a single administration to LD₅₀ for multiple administrations.

Preparations of avermectin series are widely used for therapeutic and prophylactic measures, especially in summer period, monthly, and since ivermectin and its meta

It was necessary to investigate its cumulative activity.

The aim of the study was to evaluate the supramolecular complex of ivermectin for cumulative activity according to the Federal Law of April 12, 2010 № 61-FZ "On Circulation of Medicines", which is an integral part of preclinical studies aimed at obtaining evidence of safety of new drugs.

Materials and methods

The object of the study is a supramolecular complex of ivermectin.

Characterization of the drug. With application of mechanochemical nanotechnology in impact-type grinders with adjustable energy intensity, a supramolecular complex of ivermectin for treatment of animals by free feeding in parasitosis was developed. It includes biologically active water-soluble polysaccharide arabinogalactan (AG) extracted from Siberian larch *Larix sibirica*, which is widely used in medicine and veterinary medicine. It has hepato-protective activity, is an immune

nomodulator, provides targeted drug delivery, and is used to enhance drug absorption [1, 2, 8, 12]. Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) with molecular weight $M_w \sim 12$ kDa is used in many pharmaceutical preparations to improve the solubility and bioavailability of chemotherapeutic agents.

Supramolecular complex of ivermectin is a 2% hygroscopic powder (wt. %: PVP - 49, AG - 49, ivermectin - 2) with particle size 1-10 millimicron beige color, with a weak pine odor, well soluble and suspended in water in contrast to the substance [2].

The drug was developed at the Nesmeyanov Institute of Organoelement Compounds and transferred to us by Dr. S. S. Khalikov for preclinical and clinical trials. The drug was developed at the N. A. Nesmeyanov Institute of Organoelement Compounds and transferred to us by Dr. S. S. Khalikov for preclinical and clinical trials.

The investigated substance - ivermectin in the supramolecular complex belongs to the avermectin series. The avermectin product is obtained by fermentation of the fungus *Streptomyces avermityllis*. 16-membered macrolides are secondary metabolites of *S. avermityllis*; they have a wide spectrum of nematocidal and insectocidal action and are successfully used for the prevention of parasitic diseases of humans and animals [1, 11]. The disadvantages of avermectin series preparations are species sensitivity to some animals; it is not eliminated from the body within 30 days; it affects negatively protozoa and bacteria involved in digestion, as well as co-prophagous insects.

Preliminary preclinical toxicological studies showed that supramolecular complex of ivermectin when administered enterally to white mice and applied to the skin according to GOST 12.1.00776 belongs to class IV of low toxic substances. It has no immunotoxic activity, as arabinogalactan included in the preparation contributes to the leveling of the negative effect of ivermectin in the supramolecular complex preparation on the body of animals [4].

To determine the cumulation coefficient, we used a method based on animal deaths during repeated administration of the drug - subchronic toxicity test [12] in accordance with the "Guidelines for experimental (preclinical) studies of new pharmacological substances" [10]. [10]. The advantage of this method is that it is not difficult to perform.

The cumulation coefficient ($K_{\text{кум}}$) was determined according to the formula [5]:

$$K'' = Wn) : LD5''.$$

where $LD_{50} (n)$ - mean lethal dose at n-fold administration; LD_{50} - mean lethal dose at single administration [3, 5].

The studies were conducted in the vivarium of the K. I. Skryabin All-Russian Research Institute. Animals were kept in the vivarium according to sanitary rules and on a standard diet in accordance with the established norms [7-11].

For the experiment, 20 mongrel white rats weighing 180 g were selected and divided into experimental and control groups of 10 animals each. The experimental group of rats was administered the drug orally in the first four days at a dose of 35.5 mg/kg, equal to 1/10 of the previously established single dose of LD_{50} (298.0 mg/kg), then every next four days the dose was increased 1.5 times. The control group of rats was injected with 2 ml of water each. The experiment was carried out for 28 days; throughout the experiment the animals were monitored, taking into account their condition and degree of activity. The general condition (excitation, oppression), nature and degree of activity and coordination of movements, reaction of animals to painful stimuli, presence of tremor, convulsions, paresis, paralysis, discharge from eyes, nose, urinary tract, change of skin color, change of body weight, appetite were also evaluated.

Results and discussion

As a result of studying the cumulative properties of ivermectin complex, it follows that 50% of animals died on the 22nd day of the experiment. The total dose of the administered drug for this period amounted to 1802.3 mg/kg (Table 1). The cumulation coefficient amounted to:

Table 1

Cumulative properties of the supramolecular complex of ivermectin

Days of experience	Daily dose, mg/kg	Total dose, mg/kg	Palo/live		Animal mortality, %	
			expertise	control	expertise	control
1-4	29,8	119,2	0/10	0/10	0	0
5-8	44,7	178,8	0/10	0/10	0	0
9-12	67,1	268,2	1/9	0/10	10	0
13-16	100,7	402,6	2/8	0/10	20	0
17-20	151,1	302,1	4/6	0/10	40	0
21-22	265,7	531,4	6/4	0/10	60	0
Total for 22 days	659,1	1802,3	$TO_{\text{кym}} = 1802.3 : 298 = 6.05$			

$$TO_{\text{кym}} = 1802.3 : 298.0 = 6.05.$$

In accordance with the accepted classification, the supramolecular complex of ivermectin belongs to the group of substances with weak cumulative properties, as the cumulation coefficient is equal to 6.05. Substances with $K_{\text{кym}} > 5.5$ belong to group IV of toxicity, the degree of cumulation is weak [6].

Conclusion

As a result of studying the cumulative properties of the supramolecular complex of ivermectin, the cumulation coefficient was found to be 6.05.

According to the accepted classification, supramolecular complex of ivermectin belongs to the group of substances with weak cumulative properties, as the cumulation coefficient is equal to 6.05. Substances with C_{cum} value > 5.5 belong to toxicity group IV, the degree of cumulation is weak.

Thus, the supramolecular complex of ivermectin has no cumulative action.

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